

ePIC sensitivity studies for single hadron transverse single spin asymmetry measurements for the EIC early science running

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June 16, 2026

Version 0.2
epic-AN-AC-2026-003

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Abstract

We performed feasibility studies for various single transverse spin measurements that are related to the Sivers effect, transversity and the tensor charge, and the Collins fragmentation function. The processes studied include semi-inclusive Deep inelastic scattering (SIDIS) where single hadrons (pions and kaons) were detected in addition to the scattered DIS lepton. The single hadron asymmetries were extracted as a function of the DIS variables x and Q^2 , as well as the semi-inclusive variables z , which corresponds to the momentum fraction the detected hadron carries relative to the struck parton and P_{hT} , which corresponds to the transverse momentum of the detected hadron relative to the virtual photon. They are obtained in azimuthal moments in combinations of the azimuthal angles of the hadron transverse momentum and transverse spin of the nucleon relative to the lepton scattering plane. In order to extract asymmetries, the initially unpolarized MonteCarlo was re-weighted in the true kinematic variables, hadron types and parton flavors based on global fits of fixed target SIDIS experiments and e^+e^- annihilation data. The expected statistical precision of such measurements is extrapolated to what is currently envisioned for the first five years of EIC operation. It consists of 0.5 fb^{-1} for e+p collisions of 9 on 130 GeV, 1.25 fb^{-1} for e+p collisions of 9 on 275 GeV, and 0.75 fb^{-1} for e+³He collisions of 9 on 166 GeV. For some of these energy combinations the closest fully simulated MC sets have been used. Potential systematic uncertainties are approximated given the deviations between true and reconstructed asymmetries although proper unfolding will likely reduce them significantly. Particle mis-identification is expected to be also unfolded and is currently not included in the uncertainties while some uncertainty from its unfolding can be expected.

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1 To-Do list and Changelog

1.1 To-Do list

The following tasks need to be completed still:

- reconstructed tagging of spectator protons in $e+^3\text{He}$ case
- Asymmetry reweighting in $e+^3\text{He}$ case when available
- change to correct beam energies when available

1.2 Changelog v0.1 \rightarrow v0.2

- impact figures from theorists have been added

2 Introduction

Transverse single spin asymmetries have been the key to access the transverse momentum structure of the nucleon in the past. Both of the most famous effects, the Sivers [8] effect and the Collins [9] effect were initially suggested to describe the nonzero single spin asymmetries that were seen for pions by the E704 experiment in fixed-target proton-proton collisions [10]. While in the end not directly applicable to those processes, single spin asymmetries of semi-inclusive processes did provide indications of nonzero asymmetries and both of these effects were clearly identified by the HERMES experiment in 2004 [11]. Since then these results have been confirmed in more detail by HERMES [12], COMPASS [13, 14], JLAB [15], as well as various e^+e^- results [16–19].

Apart from various related functions these two effects provide some of the main information to spin-orbit effects of the nucleon. The Sivers function describes the correlation between the transverse spin of the nucleon and the transverse momentum of a parton within it. With the expected statistics and energy range of the EIC, the precise transverse and longitudinal momentum dependent distributions of not only valence but also sea quarks and gluons can be extracted. At present only up and down quark Sivers functions are known in the valence region but with rather large uncertainties, see Fig. 1, particularly in the transverse momentum. Closely related with it is the scale dependence of the corresponding single spin asymmetries that is at present poorly known due to the fact that only fixed-target experimental data is available with very similar scales. Unlike the collinear case where at not too small momentum fractions x , the well-known DGLAP [20–22] evolution is applicable, TMD evolution, especially at low scales again relies on non-perturbative parts that are currently mostly unknown. This TMD evolution uncertainty is also aimed to be fixed based on the EIC data by both unpolarized and polarized TMD measurements.

Figure 1: Comparison of recent Siverson function extractions taken from [1], for up and down quarks as a function of x from [2–4].

While it is a common misconception that the nonzero single spin asymmetries may disappear at higher scales, in all existing fits of TMD evolution effects a logarithmic scale dependence is seen that could reduce the overall size of the asymmetries. In some of the fits the asymmetries are expected to reduce from 5-10 % in the valence region to a few % at the highest scales achievable at the EIC [4], as shown in Fig. 2 in an kinematic example where the low-scale asymmetries are only 1-2 %. As such, it is important for any EIC experiment to be able to reconstruct such asymmetries with both statistical and systematic precision below the one % level over a large kinematic range in a fine enough binning.

The Collins effect [9] relates the chiral-odd quark transversity distribution [23], that is the basis for the tensor charge, with a polarized fragmentation function, the Collins fragmentation function. It correlates the transverse spin of a fragmenting parton with the azimuthal yield of final-state hadrons around the axis of this parton. Unlike the Siverson function, that can be accessed with an unpolarized fragmentation function, the fact that the fragmentation function is also polarized and chiral-odd makes the transversity extraction more difficult. Nevertheless, access to only the Collins FF has been obtained from e^+e^- annihilation measurements, initially by Belle [16, 17] and later by BABAR [18] and [19]. Using this information together with the SIDIS data from HERMES, COMPASS and JLAB, various transversity extractions have been performed, although they predominantly rely on only valence flavors so far. Recently, also single-hadron single spin asymmetries from hadronic collisions were included in an event broader fit [2]. The interest of the tensor charges stems from the fact, that various interactions beyond the standard model may be

Figure 2: Left: example of the expected evolution effects from [4] for the Siverson asymmetry at an intermediate x and z value, as a function of Q^2 . Right: Example of expected Siverson asymmetries at the EIC as a function of x for various final-state hadrons and scales, based on the fit of [3] at $\sqrt{s} = 105\text{GeV}$.

also a tensor type of interaction [24]. As at the same time Lattice QCD calculations argue to be already fairly reliable on the calculation of the tensor charge, any discrepancies between measurement and Lattice results could indicate BSM effects. Although the tensor charges are expected to be more of a valence quark effect (due the the charges being defined as the difference of quark and antiquark transversities), fixed target measurements will not be able to perform the integral over large enough of an x range to satisfactorily extract the charges, but the EIC can [5]. Also here the scale dependence is of interest as well as accessing the sea quark transversity distributions.

3 Data selection

The simulated data was obtained using the ePIC 26.04.1 simulation campaign for the 10x130 and 10x250 e+p collisions. The generator for these events is PYTHIA6 [25] as described in [26] with similar settings that were also used in the SIDIS studies of the EIC Yellow report. The generated data that was converted into HepMC3 format and the nonzero crossing angle was included, was then run through a full GEANT4 simulation of ePIC and subsequent reconstruction. Similarly, the e+³He data was obtained from BeAGLE simulations [27] which relies also on PYTHIA6 but includes the full remnant of the nucleus which is particularly important to tag the two spectator protons for electron-neutron interactions.

The data was obtained at the energy combinations that are summarized in Table 1 where the simulations for all Q^2 were combined in several Q^2 regions where only the true Q^2 region is used assuming very small smearing given the coarse binning in this kinematic

variable. The available number of events of the simulation campaigns is specified which is typically slightly less than initially generated.

As the partonic information of the $e+^3\text{He}$ data was not yet included in the simulation campaign, the systematic uncertainties for these datasets were estimated by taking the uncertainties from the $e+p$ simulations in their corresponding kinematic bins. As can be seen from these luminosities, especially at low Q^2 the accumulated data is still far below the level of statistics to be expected from the EIC. Nevertheless the statistics are large enough to evaluate the statistical uncertainties that can be expected. At higher Q^2 , the luminosities are generally comparable or even larger than what can be expected. The expected luminosities for the first 5 years of EIC operation are also given where the square root of the luminosity ratios will be used to scale the obtained statistical uncertainties. It should be noted that in some regions the obtained number of events may be too small to calculate asymmetries in which case they do not show up in the pseudo-data but may be populated with the actual data. It should be noted that the current plan expects 9 GeV electrons instead of 10 GeV electrons and the highest proton energy will be 275 GeV instead of 250 GeV, but due to the general availability of full simulations, those closest to these values were taken, for now.

Species	Energy	Q^2 range	M events	Luminosity (fb^{-1})	ES Luminosity (fb^{-1})
e+p	10x250	1 - 10	4.97	0.007	1.25
e+p	10x250	10 - 100	4.97	0.083	
e+p	10x250	100 - 1000	4.99	2.256	
e+p	10x250	1000 - 10000	0.50	18.975	
e+p	10x130	1 - 10	4.96	0.008	0.5
e+p	10x130	10 - 100	4.98	0.105	
e+p	10x130	100 - 1000	4.97	3.425	
e+p	10x130	1000 - 10000	0.50	62.686	
$e+^3\text{He}$	10x166	2 - 10	4.94	0.024	0.75
$e+^3\text{He}$	10x166	10 - 100	4.96	0.116	
$e+^3\text{He}$	10x166	100 - 10000	4.98	3.138	

Table 1: MC statistics and luminosities used for the Single spin asymmetry simulations. The last column represents the expected luminosities during the early years of EIC operation to which all pseudo-data in this note and the corresponding impact studies are scaled.

4 General (SI)DIS kinematics, requirement

As with all deeply inelastic scattering events the typical requirements on DIS kinematics are considered. The most important one is on the scale of the process by having a lower limit on the squared momentum transfer from the lepton to the nucleon, $Q^2 > 1 \text{ GeV}^2$. Additionally, also the invariant mass of the hadronic final state is supposed to be above the main nucleon resonances which is ensured with $W^2 > 10 \text{ GeV}^2$. Also an inelasticity of $0.01 < y < 0.95$ was required. For these studies the DIS kinematics are obtained by using the reconstructed scattered lepton as obtained from the lepton finder included in the ePIC reconstruction. In some ranges of the phase-space other reconstruction methods may provide better resolutions of the kinematic variables, which will need to be considered, eventually.

In addition to the scattered lepton, at least one final-state hadron has to be detected which has been identified as either charged pion or kaon. Based on the high capabilities of the various PID detectors, it is assumed that the correct particle type can be identified via unfolding the PID misidentification matrices. While a small systematic uncertainty is expected due to this unfolding, it is not considered at this stage.

For this analysis a multi-dimensional binning in x , Q^2 , z and P_{hT} consisting of nominally $12 \times 8 \times 12 \times 12$ bins has been selected where typically bins are combined for displaying purposes but for global fits this fine binning is used directly. The bin boundaries are given in 2. Additionally, in each kinematic bin, the events are put into a two-dimensional histogram in the two azimuthal angles ϕ_S and ϕ_h with 16 equidistant bins in each dimension. Keeping both dimensions separated instead of directly using the angular combinations relevant to one particular moment reduces the amount of uncertainties that can be introduced by smearing and reconstruction effects.

Kinematic variable	Bin boundaries
x	$1.0 \times 10^{-4}, 2.154 \times 10^{-4}, 4.641 \times 10^{-4},$ $1.0 \times 10^{-3}, 2.154 \times 10^{-3}, 4.641 \times 10^{-3},$ $1.0 \times 10^{-2}, 2.154 \times 10^{-2}, 4.641 \times 10^{-2},$ $1.0 \times 10^{-1}, 2.154 \times 10^{-1}, 4.641 \times 10^{-1},$ 1.0×10^0
Q^2	$1.0 \times 10^0, 3.162 \times 10^0,$ $1.0 \times 10^1, 3.162 \times 10^1,$ $1.0 \times 10^2, 3.162 \times 10^2,$ $1.0 \times 10^3, 3.162 \times 10^3,$ 1.0×10^4
z	0,0.05,0.1,0.15,0.2,0.3,0.4, 0.5, 0.6,0.7,0.8,0.9,1.0
P_T	0,0.05,0.1,0.2,0.3,0.5, 0.7, 0.9,1.2,1.5,1.8,2.4,4.0

Table 2: Kinematic bin boundaries in the main 4-dimensional binning used for the single spin asymmetry evaluation.

5 Asymmetry analysis and reweighting

5.1 Analysis

The data is analyzed taking into account the reconstructed particles in the "ReconstructedParticles" branches for the reconstructed entries and the "MCParticles" branch for the truth entries. The reconstructed kinematics are obtained from the "InclusiveKinematicsElectron" branches and the truth kinematics from "InclusiveKinematicsTruth". Given that some beam energies and any e+A collisions the reconstructed kinematics are not filled, they are calculated by hand using the incoming particles from the MC and the scattered electron from the "MCScatteredElectronAssociations_objIdx.index" relation to the corresponding reconstructed particle.

5.2 Tagging

In the e+³He collisions, there is the possibility to explicitly tag the e+n interaction by confirming two spectator protons in the forward region. On the Truth side this is obtained simply by searching for two protons that each carry at least 70% of the nominal z momentum per nucleon. For the reconstructed events, the tagging is planned to follow [28] in finding two *tracks* in either Roman pots or Off-momentum-detectors where each track has to have hits in at least two planes of a certain detector and these hits need to be close in the transverse plane. This has yet to be implemented in the analysis code. For now only the generated event tagging was used, but given the studies in [28], high efficiencies and purities on the reconstructed side are expected that will not dilute the measurements much.

5.3 Weighting

All suitable events are reweighted based on the global fits of the SIDIS and e^+e^- data that were extracted by the Torino group [29, 30] for Sivers and Collins asymmetries, respectively.

The weights were generated based on the true x , Q^2 , z , P_T , ϕ_S , ϕ_h and the true parton flavors and hadron IDs. In the provided code, (see [31]) the structure functions for both Sivers moment (proportional to a $\sin(\phi_h - \phi_S)$ moment), Collins moment (proportional to a $\sin(\phi_h + \phi_S)$ moment) and unpolarized TMDs were extracted for each event to obtain that event's weight when filling the reconstructed distributions. Last, spin effects were applied by randomly assigning events to either spin up or spin down proton states where the spin-down weights had an additional phase of π added to invert the sign of each moments in accordance with the proton spin pointing downward instead of upward. The

total weights for each final state hadron were then given as:

$$w = 1 + A_{Coll}(x, Q^2, z, P_{hT}, q, h) \sin(\phi_h + \phi_S + spin * \pi) + A_{Siv}(x, Q^2, z, P_{hT}, q, h) \sin(\phi_h - \phi_S + spin * \pi) , \quad (1)$$

where all variables are the truth variables and histograms for both truth and reconstructed events are filled with these weights.

At the time of this global fit, not all parton flavors and hadron types were included. Generally sea quark flavors were not present in either polarized structure functions (and hence the asymmetry weights were set to unity), as were the gluons for the Sivers function (and trivially not present for transversity). Furthermore also kaons were not implemented for Collins asymmetries so also their weights were identical to zero. There is hope that eventually more parameterizations as well as uncertainties can be obtained for these structure functions such that can directly compare different sets and the variation of the resulting asymmetries.

As all parameterizations used so far were based on the unpolarized distribution or fragmentation counter parts, the same unpolarized functions had to be used in the re-weighting as well, namely GRV98 [32] for the distributions and DSS07 [33] for the fragmentation functions.

Note that at present the partonic event record is not included for the e+A simulations which means that the corresponding event weighting cannot be performed, or rather is identical with no asymmetries. The systematic uncertainties are still assigned by taking the variations between generated and reconstructed asymmetries that especially for zero asymmetries will likely be dominated by the statistical fluctuations and should be smaller in the actual measurements.

6 Reconstructed Asymmetries in relation to detector effects

6.1 Asymmetry extraction

In each kinematic bin (or for projections after combining various bins) the single spin asymmetries are calculated similar to a real experiment using the formula:

$$A_{UT}(\phi_S, \phi_h) = \frac{N^+(\phi_S, \phi_h) - N^-(\phi_S, \phi_h)}{N^+(\phi_S, \phi_h) + N^-(\phi_S, \phi_h)} \quad , \quad (2)$$

where \pm indicate the two artificially created spin states and N corresponds to the number of events in that state, kinematic and angular bin. This procedure is performed for both events in all the true kinematics as well as all the reconstructed kinematics.

The corresponding Sivers and Collins asymmetries are then fit simultaneously in a two-dimensional fit that is given by:

$$F(\phi_S, \phi_h) = A_{COL} \sin(\phi_h + \phi_S) + A_{SIV} \sin(\phi_h - \phi_S) \quad . \quad (3)$$

It is important to fit both moments simultaneously in a two-dimensional fit instead of performing one-dimensional fits in the projections as those may in principle suffer when the acceptance is not perfect.

However, examples of these one-dimensionally projected results are displayed in selected kinematic bins in Fig. 3. These figures are only for visualization purposes since they use these simplified one-dimensional azimuthal binnings. Their fits are displayed as well in that figure, but it should be noted, that those are not directly used for the physics results and impact studies as these one-dimensional projections are more prone to mis-reconstruct the actual asymmetries.

6.2 Reconstructed asymmetries

The reconstructed asymmetries are shown in various projections of fractional energy and transverse momentum for the true and the reconstructed values. One can see the projections where 2 z bins and all transverse momentum bins were combined in Fig. 4. In these z -dependent asymmetry figures, also the introduced asymmetries as shown as a histogram. As can be seen, the statistics for even the generated asymmetries is sometimes not large enough to fully obtain the introduced asymmetries (or only with significant fluctuations around those). In the future, slightly higher MC statistics would help to reduce these uncertainties. Overall, one can see that with increasing x and Q^2 , the magnitude of the asymmetries is increasing which is expected due to the existing nonzero measurements coming only from the intermediately high x region, so far. Consequently, the pion Collins asymmetries are of opposite sign for the charges and appear to be increasing with momentum fraction. For the Sivers asymmetries the positive pions are positive while the negative pions are for the most part close to zero, but eventually turn negative. The reconstructed asymmetries generally track the introduced asymmetries fairly well, given the statistical limitations.

Figure 3: Top: One-dimensional azimuthal asymmetry projection for the Collins type modulation as a function of the angular combination $\phi_h + \phi_S$ are shown for the specified x , Q^2 bins, integrated over transverse momentum and in an intermediate z bin. True and reconstructed data shown for positive pions (black and green respectively) and negative pions (blue and magenta, respectively). The fits to the sine modulations are displayed as well in the corresponding colors. Middle: Extracted Collins-type asymmetries in the same x and Q^2 bins, integrated over P_T and displayed as a function of z . Bottom: Extracted Collins-type asymmetries in the same x and Q^2 bins, integrated over z and displayed as a function of P_T .

Figure 4: Collins asymmetries as a function of z in bins of x and Q^2 for 10 GeV electrons on 250 protons for positive (black, green) and negative (blue, purple) pions. The asymmetries in the true kinematics are shown in black and blue symbols while the asymmetries in the reconstructed kinematics are shown in blue and purple symbols.

Figure 5: Sivers asymmetries as a function of z in bins of x and Q^2 for 10 GeV electrons on 250 protons for positive (black, green) and negative (blue, purple) pions. The asymmetries in the true kinematics are shown in black and blue symbols while the asymmetries in the reconstructed kinematics are shown in blue and purple symbols.

Figure 6: Collins asymmetries as a function of z in bins of x and Q^2 for 10 GeV electrons on 130 protons for positive (black, green) and negative (blue, purple) pions. The asymmetries in the true kinematics are shown in black and blue symbols while the asymmetries in the reconstructed kinematics are shown in blue and purple symbols.

Figure 7: Sivers asymmetries as a function of z in bins of x and Q^2 for 10 GeV electrons on 130 protons for positive (black, green) and negative (blue, purple) pions. The asymmetries in the true kinematics are shown in black and blue symbols while the asymmetries in the reconstructed kinematics are shown in blue and purple symbols.

7 Projected asymmetries and estimate of systematic uncertainties

After extracting the weighted asymmetries in the given statistics, a next step is to extrapolate these measurements to the full statistics that are aimed for at the EIC. In this study it was assumed that at each collision energy 1.25, 0.5, and 0.75 fb⁻¹ can be obtained for the respective beam energy and species combinations and in the projection figures all statistical uncertainties were scaled to this luminosity. For the systematic uncertainties a similar approach as in the EIC yellow report has been chosen, where as a conservative estimate the differences between true and reconstructed asymmetries based on the re-weighting were assigned. This estimate is for the most part clearly too conservative as in reality an unfolding of the asymmetries would be performed. However, such an unfolding would require substantially more, and preferably independent, MC simulations as well as a much more detailed description of all detector components, etc. Even in an unfolding procedure, if the discrepancies between true and reconstructed asymmetries get large (i.e. larger off-diagonal elements in the smearing matrix), also the uncertainties in the unfolding will increase and therefore taking at this point these differences as uncertainties is a prudent, albeit conservative approach.

An example of the expected uncertainties in three select x and Q^2 bins are shown in Figs.8 and 9 for the highest collision energies for Collins and Sivers asymmetries, respectively. Already from this simple figure one can take away several important aspects of the expected uncertainties using the EIC and in particular ePIC, even from the early EIC operation. At low values of x and Q^2 the cross sections are largest and therefore the statistical uncertainties are generally very small, however as the expected asymmetries are also expected to be well below the one per-cent level there, such precision is quite necessary. One also sees that at combinations of higher transverse momenta or fractional energies the systematic uncertainties are increasing which is likely related to the smearing in these two kinematic variables, given that the azimuthal angles do not show larger smearing effects. This behavior is even more prominent when going toward higher x and Q^2 where also the smearing in x and Q^2 is becoming more relevant. In terms of statistical uncertainties the expected uncertainties stay below the one per-cent level as long as neither z nor P_T become too large.

A simplified display of the expected uncertainties for all x and Q^2 bins are shown in Fig. 10 for the Sivers asymmetries at the highest collision energy and in Fig. 11 for the Collins asymmetries where for visibility 2 z bins and 4 P_T bins were combined. As can be seen, a sub % level of precision can be reached over a large range of x and Q^2 bins, with this collision energy mostly covering the lower x and the higher Q^2 bins best. Following the z dependence of fragmentation functions the statistical and systematic uncertainties tend to increase toward higher z while also the uncertainties at higher transverse momenta are generally the largest likely following similar reasons.

The lower collision energies move successively further toward the bottom right of the x - Q^2 plane with the lowest collision energy covering the highest x and lowest Q^2 , as can

Figure 8: Projected π^+ Collins asymmetry statistical and systematic uncertainties as a function of either z (top panel) in bins of P_T or as a function of P_T in bins of z (bottom panel) for three select x and Q^2 bins. The asymmetries are shown at arbitrary values for better visibility. The statistical uncertainties are extrapolated to an accumulated luminosity of 1.25 fb^{-1} for the 10 GeV \times 250 GeV energy option. For better visibility either 4 bins in P_T and 2 bins in z were combined or vice versa.

be seen in Figs. 12 and 13 for Sivers and Collins asymmetries, respectively. Due to the generally lower center-of-mass energy, the phase space for larger transverse momenta is substantially reduced at higher x and thus only precise measurements for transverse momenta below 1.2 GeV are possible there. However, the missing transverse momenta would anyway fall outside of the region that could be interpreted via TMDs [34].

A simple visualization of just the uncertainties for all 4 dimensional bins for pions is shown in Fig. 16. One can see that even in such a fine binning a sub per-cent level statistical precision can be reached, predominantly at lower x and Q^2 and for lower transverse momenta and momentum fractions. However, over the whole phase-space the expected precision is still on the % level except for the phase-space boundaries in z and P_T . Even for the less abundant negative kaons, the statistical precision is still reasonable for most of the phase-space, as shown in Fig. 17/

Figure 9: Projected π^+ Sivers asymmetry statistical and systematic uncertainties as a function of either z (top panel) in bins of P_T or as a function of P_T in bins of z (bottom panel) for three select x and Q^2 bins. The asymmetries are shown at arbitrary values for better visibility. The statistical uncertainties are extrapolated to an accumulated luminosity of 1.25 fb^{-1} for the 10 GeV x 250 GeV energy option. For better visibility either 4 bins in P_T and 2 bins in z were combined or vice versa.

7.1 Q^2 dependence of asymmetries

Another important aspect of the transverse spin single spin asymmetries is the study of their scale dependence. For those it is important to have as large a Q^2 lever arm at an x value where the asymmetries are not too small at low scales. While the number of beam energy combinations in the first several years of EIC running will be limited, a decent range in Q^2 can still be covered as highlighted in Fig. 18.

Figure 10: Projected π^+ Sivers asymmetry statistical and systematic uncertainties as a function of z in bins of P_T , x and Q^2 shown at arbitrary asymmetry values for better visibility. The statistical uncertainties are extrapolated to an accumulated luminosity of 1.25 fb^{-1} for the 10 GeV x 250 GeV energy option.

Figure 11: Projected π^+ Collins asymmetry statistical and systematic uncertainties as a function of z in bins of P_T , x and Q^2 shown at arbitrary asymmetry values for better visibility. The statistical uncertainties are extrapolated to an accumulated luminosity of 1.25 fb^{-1} for the 10 GeV x 250 GeV energy option.

Figure 12: Projected π^+ Sivers asymmetry statistical and systematic uncertainties as a function of z in bins of P_T , x and Q^2 shown at arbitrary asymmetry values for better visibility. The statistical uncertainties are extrapolated to an accumulated luminosity of 0.5 fb^{-1} for the 10 GeV x 130 GeV energy option.

Figure 13: Projected π^+ Collins asymmetry statistical and systematic uncertainties as a function of z in bins of P_T , x and Q^2 shown at arbitrary asymmetry values for better visibility. The statistical uncertainties are extrapolated to an accumulated luminosity of 0.5 fb^{-1} for the 10 GeV x 130 GeV energy option.

Figure 14: Projected π^+ Sivers asymmetry statistical and systematic uncertainties as a function of z in bins of P_T , x and Q^2 shown at arbitrary asymmetry values for better visibility. The statistical uncertainties are extrapolated to an accumulated luminosity of 0.75 fb^{-1} for the $e + {}^3\text{He}$ 10 GeV x 166 GeV energy option.

Figure 15: Projected π^+ Collins asymmetry statistical and systematic uncertainties as a function of z in bins of P_T , x and Q^2 shown at arbitrary asymmetry values for better visibility. The statistical uncertainties are extrapolated to an accumulated luminosity of 0.75 fb^{-1} for the $e + {}^3\text{He}$ 10 GeV x 166 GeV energy option.

Figure 16: Projected π^+ Collins asymmetry statistical uncertainties as a function of z and P_T in bins of x and Q^2 . The statistical uncertainties are extrapolated to an accumulated luminosity of 1.25 fb^{-1} for the 10 GeV x 250 GeV energy option.

Figure 17: Projected K^- Collins asymmetry statistical uncertainties as a function of z and P_T in bins of x and Q^2 . The statistical uncertainties are extrapolated to an accumulated luminosity of 1.25 fb^{-1} for the 10 GeV x 250 GeV energy option.

Figure 18: Projected π^+ Collins asymmetry uncertainties as a function of Q^2 in bins of x and integrated over P_T and z shown at arbitrary asymmetry values for better visibility. The statistical uncertainties are extrapolated to an accumulated luminosity of 0.5 fb^{-1} for both beam energy options.

8 Impact of pseudo-data

8.1 Siverson function measurements:

The extraction of the Siverson TMDs was performed by many groups [1, 3, 30, 35–44]. However, the general knowledge is still very limited due to having for the most part only data from fixed target experiments. This means that at the moment only the valence region and only at relatively small scales has been accessed while sea quarks, gluons and even the lower- x region of the valence quarks are not well understood.

For the present impact study we used pseudo-data for π^\pm and K^\pm production in $e + p$ collisions at the highest (10×250 GeV) and (10×130 GeV) energy configurations, as well as $e + {}^3\text{He}$ data at (10×166 GeV), scaled to 1.25 fb^{-1} , 0.5 fb^{-1} , and 0.75 fb^{-1} according to the expected energies and luminosities that can be obtained in the first several years of the EIC. The systematic uncertainties were estimated as previously described by the differences between generated and reconstructed asymmetries. The resulting pseudo-data set has about two orders of magnitude more points than current data. Performing the fit of pseudo-data with the initial setup of the Siverson function from the global analysis made in Ref. [44] based on SIDIS [45–49] and Drell-Yan [50, 51] data, we observe a sizeable reduction of uncertainties, as shown in Fig. 19. The uncertainty bands can be reduced significantly for all flavors, even with these fairly limited statistics, compared to what is expected over a longer period of operating the EIC.

The impact studies based on these uncertainties can be seen in Fig 19 for the Siverson functions and their corresponding transverse momentum moments, the EQTS functions. They show the expected uncertainties of the up and down quark Siverson functions in comparison to the current knowledge as extracted from [4]. It should be noted, that the pseudo-data below $x < 0.01$ was not yet used in this impact study but given that it represents a significant part of the future EIC measurements, more impact can be expected in this region.

Measuring the P_T -dependence of the asymmetries for a given (x, z, Q) bin allows for the determination of the k_T -shape of the Siverson function, which is currently hardly constrained at all by experimental data. This can be seen highlighted in Fig. 20, where the current and expected uncertainties on the Siverson function in b -space (the Fourier transform of the intrinsic transverse momentum) is shown. A significant reduction is visible even with the still fairly limited precision of the expected early science data.

8.2 Collins-function-based transversity measurements:

The tensor charges and the (chiral-odd) transversity distributions are the third leading-twist quantity of the nucleon. They can only be accessed in combination with chiral-odd counter parts such as the Collins fragmentation function [9]. Several results from fixed-target SIDIS measurements, e^+e^- annihilation and, recently, polarized proton-proton collisions, were included in various global fits [52–55], but the uncertainties are still very substantial. Using the framework of the QCD global analysis of transverse SSAs devel-

Figure 19: Top: Expected impact on up and down quark Sivers distributions, displayed as the EQTS momentum, as a function of x , obtained from SIDIS pion and kaon EIC pseudodata, at the scale of 2 GeV from the expected early science running. The orange-shaded areas represent the current uncertainty, while the grey-shaded areas are the uncertainties when including the early science EIC pseudodata. Bottom: Same but showing the relative uncertainties to the size of the functions themselves before and after inclusion of the early science data.

oped in Ref. [2] and updated in [56, 57] (JAM22), the impact of the EIC single-hadron Collins effect SIDIS data on the transversity distributions and the tensor charges was determined (see Fig. 21). Again, PYTHIA 6 was used to generate pseudodata for both proton and ^3He beams at various energies and scaled to 1.25 fb^{-1} , 0.5 fb^{-1} , and 0.75 fb^{-1} for the previously mentioned beam energy and species combinations expected during the early science running at the EIC. The pseudodata were then re-weighted using structure functions based on the extraction presented in Ref. [52]. The Collins asymmetries are given by the $\sin(\phi_h + \phi_S)$ modulation of the cross section. The JAM22 fit utilizes the connection between TMDs and twist-3 multi-parton correlators to simultaneously fit data from SIDIS [11, 58], e^+e^- annihilation [18, 59–63], Drell-Yan [50, 51], and SSAs in proton-proton

Figure 20: Expected impact on the up (blue) and down (brown) Sivers functions as a function of b - the Fourier transform to the transverse momentum. The darker shaded regions show the impact of the early science data.

collisions [64, 65]. A sizeable reduction of the uncertainties is visible even with the still very limited statistics expected in the early years of EIC operation.

The importance of the polarized ^3He data is also manifest, especially for the down-quark transversity. Further details can be found in Ref. [5] for similar studies using the full expected EIC statistics. With the EIC data, uncertainties for phenomenological extractions of the tensor charges will become comparable to, and possibly smaller than, current lattice QCD calculations (see, e.g., Ref. [6, 7]). As such, potential discrepancies may become relevant for searches of physics beyond the Standard Model [24, 66]. We also mention that there is a significant reduction in the uncertainty for the Collins function (see Fig. 21), which will be an important test of universality with results from e^+e^- annihilation. (Theoretical considerations suggest that TMD fragmentation functions are universal, based on the specific kinematics of the fragmentation process — see, for example, Refs. [67, 68].) In addition, Fig. 21 shows $g_T^{[x_{min}]}$ vs. x_{min} , where $g_T^{[x_{min}]}$ is the following truncated integral: $g_T^{[x_{min}]} \equiv \int_{x_{min}}^1 dx [(h_1^u(x) - h_1^{\bar{u}}(x)) - (h_1^d(x) - h_1^{\bar{d}}(x))]$, as well as the reduction in the uncertainty of this quantity from the baseline fit of JAM20 [2]. With the EIC the expectation is that the uncertainty will go down to 10% of JAM22.

Figure 21: Top: Expected impact on the up and down quark transversity distributions and favored and unfavored Collins function first moment when including the early science EIC Collins effect SIDIS pseudo-data from $e+p$ and $e+^3\text{He}$ collisions [5]. Bottom left: Plot of the truncated integral $g_T^{[x_{min}]}$ vs. x_{min} . Also shown is the ratio $\Delta_{\text{EIC}}/\Delta_{\text{JAM20}}$ of the uncertainty in $g_T^{[x_{min}]}$ for the re-fit that includes pseudodata from

9 Outlook of further studies

This note has described the extraction of pseudo-data and impact studies for the early science report, based on the 26.04.1 campaign. It shows that even in the first several years of EIC operation, sub-percent level uncertainties can be obtained on the azimuthal single spin asymmetries related to the Sivers and Collins effects. It shows that despite the limited statistics, significant improvements are already possible.

As the collision energies were recently changed, the note will be updated accordingly with the appropriate energies. Also the actual parton information of the $e+^3\text{He}$ will be included when it is fixed in future simulation campaigns.

Furthermore, a similar note will be prepared for the full scope of the EIC, including more beam energy combinations which should improve the impact of the Sivers and Tensor charge extractions significantly.

One aspect that needs to be eventually studied is the effect of radiative corrections. Especially at high y it is expected to be substantial and could alter the range of covered transverse momenta and momentum fractions. Also the explicit correction of detector smearing effects will need to be investigated using multi-dimensional unfolding techniques as soon as the detector description and event reconstruction have matured and large-scale simulations are available to cover the phase-space with reasonable statistics.

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